

EFFECT OF THE SKIN-CORE INTERPHASE PROPERTIES ON THE TENSILE STRESS DISTRIBUTION FIELD OF AN AL-GFRP SANDWICH BEAM

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Sandwich beams widely used since the beginning of the century on various structures combine perfect specific bending properties. A new family of sandwich laminates with improved specific tensile strength, consisted of metal alloys as facings and composite laminates as core, was lately developed. These new laminates are widely used as basic structural materials on several applications. Even though epoxy systems offer elevated adhesion quality, the weak point of sandwich beams, i.e. the interlaminar layer, is still present. On of the main drawbacks in utilising multilayer area. An improper interlayer area may lead to premature failure of the whole structure. A similar system consisted of aluminum facings and glass/epoxy core was subjected to analytical and experimental investigations with emphasis on the stress distribution along the beam length, as affected by the different material properties and the bonding conditions. The introduction of a new coefficient, strongly related to the degree of layer adhesion as well as to the difference of the shear modulus between core and facings, leads this new approach closer to reality, when in contrary, the majority of the existing approaches assume a perfect interlayer bonding. Moreover the distribution of the applied normal stresses at the beam edges, which usually in neglected, is now taken into account. Finally, a parametric study referring to real experimental conditions, lead to useful conclusions for the proper designing of such sandwich systems.